

Shallow-water wave rays as geodesics of an optical metric

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Abstract

We show that the classical refraction of shallow-water surface waves over variable bathymetry can be recast in terms of geodesic motion in a two-dimensional optical metric. Starting from Fermat's principle, we construct the conformal metric $g_{ij}^{\text{opt}} = n^2(x, y)\delta_{ij}$ with index $n = 1/\sqrt{gh}$. We derive the explicit Christoffel symbols, recover the continuous Snell law, and obtain a closed-form expression for ray trajectories on a plane beach. The Gaussian curvature of the optical metric, $K_{\text{opt}} = (gh/2)\Delta \ln h$, provides a compact criterion for ray convergence near shoals and divergence on uniform slopes. This geometrical framework naturally connects wave refraction to differential geometry, offering a concise and rigorous language for coastal wave dynamics.

1 Introduction

Wave refraction over variable bathymetry is traditionally described by the continuous Snell law in shallow water [?, ?]. Here we reformulate the problem in terms of geodesics of an *optical metric*, following Fermat's principle. This approach, standard in optics [?] and in general relativity, has not been explicitly applied to shallow-water surface waves in oceanography.

2 Optical metric from Fermat's principle

The travel time along a curve Γ is

$$T[\Gamma] = \int_{\Gamma} \frac{ds}{c(\mathbf{x})} = \int_{\Gamma} n(\mathbf{x}) ds, \quad n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{gh(\mathbf{x})}}.$$

Define the conformal optical metric

$$g_{ij}^{\text{opt}}(x, y) = n^2(x, y)\delta_{ij} = e^{2\phi(x, y)}\delta_{ij}, \quad \phi = \ln n.$$

Stationary optical length corresponds to geodesic motion in g^{opt} .

3 Christoffel symbols and geodesics

For $g_{ij} = e^{2\phi}\delta_{ij}$ in 2D,

$$\Gamma_{jk}^i = \delta_k^i \partial_j \phi + \delta_j^i \partial_k \phi - \delta_{jk} \partial^i \phi.$$

Explicit components:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{xx}^x &= \partial_x \phi, \quad \Gamma_{yy}^x = -\partial_x \phi, \quad \Gamma_{xy}^x = \Gamma_{yx}^x = \partial_y \phi, \\ \Gamma_{yy}^y &= \partial_y \phi, \quad \Gamma_{xx}^y = -\partial_y \phi, \quad \Gamma_{xy}^y = \Gamma_{yx}^y = \partial_x \phi. \end{aligned}$$

The geodesic equations reproduce the Fermat ray equations:

$$\frac{d\hat{\mathbf{s}}}{ds} = \nabla \ln c - (\nabla \ln c \cdot \hat{\mathbf{s}})\hat{\mathbf{s}}.$$

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4 Continuous Snell law

If $h = h(x)$ (bathymetry invariant alongshore), the momentum

$$p_y = n(x) \sin \theta$$

is conserved, yielding

$$n(x) \sin \theta(x) = \frac{\sin \theta(x)}{c(x)} = \text{const.}$$

5 Plane beach example

For $h(x) = h_0 - \alpha x$,

$$c(x) = \sqrt{g(h_0 - \alpha x)}, \quad \sin \theta(x) = \sqrt{\frac{h_0 - \alpha x}{h_0}} \sin \theta_0.$$

The trajectory integrates to

$$y(x) = y_0 + \frac{h_0}{\alpha \sin^2 \theta_0} \left[\theta_0 - \sin \theta_0 \cos \theta_0 - \phi(x) + \sin \phi(x) \cos \phi(x) \right],$$

with $\phi(x) = \arcsin(\sin \theta_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{\alpha}{h_0} x})$.

6 Optical curvature and focusing

For $g = e^{2\phi}(dx^2 + dy^2)$,

$$K_{\text{opt}} = -e^{-2\phi} \Delta \phi = \frac{gh}{2} \Delta \ln h.$$

Uniform slopes have $K_{\text{opt}} < 0$, while localized shoals yield $K_{\text{opt}} > 0$ (ray convergence).

7 Figures

Figure 1: Top-down schematic

Figure 2: Optical metric geometry

8 Conclusions

Shallow-water wave rays can be rigorously formulated as geodesics of the optical metric $g^{\text{opt}} = n^2 \delta_{ij}$. The Christoffel symbols reproduce the Fermat ray equations, the continuous Snell law emerges as a conserved momentum, and the Gaussian curvature controls convergence.

References

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